

Hetero-Ring Formations with Thio-Carbohydrazide

Part II

Condensations with Diketones and Aldehydes

BY

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In a previous communication (this *Journal*, 1924, 1, 141) a number of cases of hetero-ring formations with thiocarbohydrazide has been described. The present investigation was undertaken with the object of making a comparative study of the behaviour of *ortho*-diketones with hydrazine, urea, semicarbazide on the one hand and with thiocarbohydrazide on the other. Curtius and his collaborators (*J. pr. Chem.*, 44, 169, 188; *Ber.*, 22, 2161) obtained different types of compounds from varying quantities of hydrazine hydrate and several *ortho*-diketones. Interesting bridged-ring compounds have been obtained from glyoxal and some *ortho*-diketones by the action of carbamide by Bottinger (*Ber.*, 10, 1923); Schiff (*Annalen*, 189, 15), Franchimont and Klobie (*R.* 7, 251), Angeli (*Gazetta*, 19, 563; *Ber.*, 24, 606), Anschutz and Geldermann (*Annalen*, 261, 129). Again Thiele and Stanger obtained a triazine compound from benzil and thiosemicarbazide and later on, Bromberg (*Ber.*, 30, 132) obtained an additive compound and a semicarbazone with alloxan and its dimethyl derivative. Schmidt and Sauer (*Ber.*, 44, 3250), Schmidt, Schainer and Glatz (*Ber.*, 44, 276) obtained a semicarbazone

from phenanthraquinone and a triazine compound from its monoxime.

One molecule of thiocarbohydrazide reacts with one of benzil, acenaphthaquinone, camphorquinone and alloxan with the formation of compounds which may be regarded as closed ring thiocarbohydrazones (I).

Now it is a well-known fact that when an atomic grouping $-\text{NH}-\text{CS}-\text{NH}-$ is present in a compound, especially when it forms part of a ring, the compound, by virtue of the presence of the potential mercaptanic group, dissolves in alkalis and forms disulphides and thio-ethers. But it is curious to note that the supposed cyclic compounds so formed do not exhibit any mercaptanic properties, which precludes the possibility of the above atomic grouping being present and hence the present authors suggest the alternative constitution (II), which would result from the migration of two hydrogen atoms. Similar cases of migration resulting in the change of hydrazones into azo-compounds are well-known.

In the case of phenanthraquinone and isatin two molecules react with one molecule of thiocarbohydrazide yielding compounds of the type,

only one ketonic group of the diketones being reactive. The compounds so formed are also found to be insoluble

in alkalis. In order to account for a similar phenomenon, *viz.*, the insolubility of benzene-azo- β -naphthol or β -naphthaquinone phenylhydrazone in alkali, different non-hydroxylic formulae have been suggested by Liebermann (*Ber.*, 16, 2863), Zincke and Lawson (*Ber.*, 20, 2903) and Meldola (*Phil. Mag.*, 1888, 11, 411); and by analogy with the view of Liebermann the present authors assign to their compounds the modified formula,

The monoxime of isatin reacts with thiocarbohydrazide forming a normal thiocarbohydrazone of the oxime, which in its turn furnishes a thio-keto-bis-triazole compound when heated in a sealed tube with concentrated hydrochloric acid, thus:

Phenanthraquinone-monoxime gives the triazole compound at once and the intermediate oxime-thiocarbohydrazone is not isolated. The above type of bis-triazole compounds are insoluble in alkali and form black sulphide of mercury with mercuric oxide, showing respectively the absence of any mercaptanic group and the presence of the sulphur atom in the thio-ketonic form.

Thiocarbohydrazide yields compounds of the type $\text{CS}(\text{NH.N}=\text{CR.R}^1)_2$ with aldehydes and ketones. Attempts to condense one molecule of the hydrazide with one of the aldehyde or ketone have been unsuccessful. Benzaldehyde, *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde, salicylaldehyde, cinnamic aldehyde, anisaldehyde, furfural, piperonal, acetone, methylethyl ketone, acetophenone and benzophenone have been condensed with thiocarbohydrazide.

The thiocarbohydrazones of the aldehydes and ketones have been found to give rise to an interesting class of compounds with acid chlorides, esters of α -halogenated acids and α -halogenated ketones which in their turn are expected to form interesting fused-ring heterocyclic compounds with suitable reagents. The action of *o*-diketones on carbohydrazide and thiosemicarbazides is also under investigation and in a few cases, interesting results have already been obtained.

EXPERIMENTAL.

3-Thioketo-6:7-diphenyl-1:2:4:5-heptatetrazine.

A mixture of benzil (1 part), thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride (1 part) and glacial acetic acid was heated under reflux. The reaction began at once as was indicated by the gradual disappearance of the hydrazide hydrochloride, which is insoluble in this solvent. On continued heating the solution became first yellow and then brown and after many hours deposited a small crop of light yellow crystals. This was filtered and washed with water and acetone. It melts at 118° – 120° . The yield is extremely poor. (Found : N = 20.32. $C_{15}H_{12}N_4S$ requires N = 20.00 per cent.)

It is insoluble in water, acetone, benzene; very soluble in alcohol and pyridine from which it could not, however, be crystallised. It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids and caustic alkalis. The mother-liquor on dilution with water deposited a brown resinous mass which was extremely soluble in all organic solvents. An attempt to isolate a second product from this resinous mass was attended with failure.

3-Thioketo-acenaphth a-1:2:4:5-heptatetrazine.

A mixture of acenaphthaquinone (1 part) and thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride (1 part) was heated with acetic acid under reflux for 2 to 3 hours. The solid mass so formed was separated by filtration from the mother-liquor while hot and washed with acetic acid and water. It was then purified by crystallisation either from boiling nitrobenzene or from pyridine. As obtained from these solvents it possesses a dark brown colour and melts at 253°. (Found : N=22·41. $C_{13}H_8N_4S$ requires N=22·22 per cent.)

It is insoluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene and acetic acid ; soluble in pyridine and nitrobenzene. It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids and caustic alkalis. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it with a dark brown colour.

3-Thioketo-camphor-1:2:4:5-hepta-tetrazine.

A mixture of camphorquinone (1 part) and thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride (1 part) was heated with glacial acetic acid under reflux for several hours. The solution became first yellow and then reddish-brown and after filtering and allowing to cool and stand, deposited a light yellow precipitate which was separated and crystallised from nitrobenzene. It was thus obtained as yellow needles which did not melt even at 290°. (Found : N=23·82. $C_{11}H_{16}N_4S$ requires N=23·73 per cent.)

It is insoluble in acetone, benzene, and chloroform ; readily soluble in alcohol and fairly soluble in acetic acid or boiling nitrobenzene. It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids and caustic alkalis. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it producing a yellow colouration.

3-Thioketo-alloxan-1:2:4:5-hepta-tetrazine.

When a mixture of alloxan (1 part), thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride (1 part) and glacial acetic acid was

heated under reflux there separated an orange coloured substance in the course of 4 to 5 minutes. The mixture was further heated for about half an hour and the solid mass was separated from the hot mother-liquor by suction. It was then washed with acetic acid and water and finally crystallised from pyridine in pale orange crystals which did not melt even at 295° . (Found: N=39.69. $C_8H_4O_2N_2S$ requires N=39.62 per cent.)

It is insoluble in water, acetic acid, acetone, alcohol, nitrobenzene and benzene; readily soluble in hot pyridine. It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids and dissolves readily in caustic soda. Concentrated sulphuric acid dissolves it with a brown colour.

Di-phenanthraquinone-thiocarbohydrazone.

Thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride (1 part) was mixed with phenanthraquinone (2 parts) dissolved in glacial acetic acid and heated under reflux when a reaction began at once and the solution turned red. Red crystals began to separate out after 2 to 3 minutes and for the completion of the reaction heating was continued for a further period of 15 to 20 mins. The red precipitate was boiled with acetic acid to remove excess of phenanthraquinone, and unchanged theocarbonylhydrazide hydrochloride was removed by washing with water. The hydrazone so obtained possesses a beautiful vermilion colour, and is sufficiently pure for analysis; it melts at 242° . (Found: N=11.49. $C_{22}H_{18}O_2N_4S$ requires N=11.52 per cent.)

When the substance is crystallised from pyridine its colour becomes lighter. The needle-shaped crystals thus obtained contain one molecule of pyridine of crystallisation. (Found: N=12.59. $C_{24}H_{22}O_2N_4S$ requires N=12.39 per cent.)

Di-β-naphthaquinone-thiocarbohydrazone.

A mixture of β-naphthaquinone (2 parts) and thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride (1 part) was heated with acetic acid under reflux for about an hour and a half. The black solid mass thus formed was filtered off from the hot solution and was washed with water. It was then extracted with pyridine and the solution boiled with animal charcoal. The filtrate gave a grey-coloured flocculent amorphous precipitate on the addition of water. In order to purify it further, it was dissolved in boiling nitrobenzene from which a grey-coloured amorphous mass was obtained which did not melt even at 290°. (Found: N = 14.04; S = 7.85. $C_{22}H_{14}O_2N_4S$ requires N = 14.51; S = 8.29 per cent.)

It is insoluble in water, acetic acid, alcohol, acetone and benzene; readily soluble in pyridine and nitrobenzene: insoluble in dilute mineral acids and caustic alkalis and is charred by concentrated sulphuric acid.

Di-isatin-thiocarbohydrazone.

A mixture of isatin (2 parts) and thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride (1 part) was heated in acetic acid for about half an hour when there separated a deep orange-coloured precipitate which was filtered off from the mother-liquor, washed successively with acetic acid and water and finally crystallised from boiling nitrobenzene in orange-coloured needles which melted with decomposition at 262°. (Found: N = 23.52. $C_{17}H_{13}O_2N_4S$ requires N = 23.07 per cent.)

It is insoluble in water, acetone, benzene, chloroform and acetic acid; almost insoluble in alcohol; readily soluble in pyridine and boiling nitrobenzene and insoluble in dilute mineral acids. It can be precipitated by hydrochloric acid from the red coloured solution which it forms with dilute caustic alkalis. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a violet-red colour.

Thiocarbohydrazone of Diacetyl monoxime.

Diacetyl monoxime (2 parts), thiocarbonylhydrazide hydrochloride (1 part) and acetic acid were heated under reflux for about 5 to 6 hours, after which the filtered solution was allowed to stand over-night. As no solid separated out, the acetic acid solution was diluted with water when a grey coloured amorphous mass was precipitated. This was filtered and washed with water. In order to purify it further, a pyridine solution of this substance was boiled with animal charcoal and the filtered solution on dilution with water, deposited an amorphous precipitate which chars at 220° and then melts at 285°. It could not be crystallised from any organic solvent. (Found: N=31.11; S=12.02. $C_6H_{10}O_2N_2S$ requires N=30.88; S=11.76 per cent.)

It is insoluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene and chloroform; readily soluble in acetic acid and pyridine. It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids but dissolves in dilute caustic alkalis with the formation of a red coloured solution.

Thioketo-bis-dimethyl-triazole.

When the above oxime-hydrazone was heated with glacial acetic acid containing concentrated hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube at 100° for five to six hours, it was converted into an insoluble solid mass. This was filtered and washed with water till free from acids. It could not be crystallised from any organic solvent and it does not melt at 300°. (Found: N=35.82; S=13.28 $C_6H_{12}N_4S$ requires N=35.59; S=13.56 per cent.)

It is insoluble in most organic solvents; dilute mineral acids and caustic alkalis have no solvent action upon it.

Thioketo-bis-phenanthratriazole.

A mixture of phenanthraquinone monoxime (2 parts) and thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride (1 part) was heated under reflux with acetic acid. The reaction began on gentle warming with the separation of a reddish brown crystalline mass. Heating was continued for about half an hour when the reaction came to an end. The precipitate was separated from the hot mother-liquor, washed repeatedly with hot acetic acid and then with water in order to free it from any unchanged reacting materials. It was crystallised from boiling nitrobenzene in needles melting at 230° . (Found: N=18.03. $C_{28}H_{18}N_6S$ requires N=17.50 per cent.)

It is insoluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene, chloroform and acetic acid; readily soluble in boiling nitrobenzene and pyridine; insoluble in dilute mineral acids. It dissolves very sparingly in boiling dilute caustic soda with a pink colour. In concentrated sulphuric acid, it dissolves without charring with a brown colour.

Thiocarbohydrazone of Isatoxime.

Thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride (1 part) was added to a solution of isatoxime (2 parts) in boiling glacial acetic acid. The solution soon turned red. The mixture was heated for about three hours for the completion of the reaction, filtered and allowed to stand over-night, when greenish yellow needles were deposited. These were separated from the mother-liquor by filtration and washed with water to remove the excess of hydrazide hydrochloride. For further purification it was crystallised from nitrobenzene in yellow needles which melt with decomposition at 228° . (Found: N=28.76. $C_{17}H_{14}O_2N_6S$ requires N=28.43 per cent.)

It is insoluble in water, acetone and benzene; readily soluble in alcohol, acetic acid and nitrobenzene; insoluble in dilute mineral acids but readily soluble in dilute caustic soda with a red colouration from which it can be precipitated again by hydrochloric acid. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a deep red colour.

Thioketo-bis-isatintriazole.

When the above oxime-hydrazone was heated with alcoholic hydrochloric acid in a sealed tube at 100° for several hours it was converted into an insoluble solid mass which was filtered off washed with alcohol to remove any unconverted oxime-hydrazone and finally crystallised from pyridine in yellow needles with a greenish tinge which do not melt at 290°. (Found: N=31.58. $C_{17}H_{10}N_8S$ requires N=31.28 per cent.)

It is insoluble in alcohol, acetone, benzene and chloroform; sparingly soluble in acetic acid; readily in pyridine and nitrobenzene. It is insoluble in dilute mineral acids, or alkalis. It dissolves in concentrated sulphuric acid with a red colour.

CONDENSATION WITH KETONES AND ALDEHYDES.

Dibenzylidene-thiocarbohydrazone.

To an aqueous solution of one gram of thiocarbohydrazone hydrochloride was added an alcoholic solution of two grams of benzaldehyde with frequent shaking. The reaction began at once with the separation of a slightly yellowish amorphous flocculent precipitate. This was filtered off, washed with alcohol and crystallised from boiling acetic acid in which the dibenzylidene compound is moderately soluble. It melts at 194°. (Found: S=11.14. $C_{15}H_{14}N_4S$ requires S=11.35 per cent.)

The dibenzylidene-thiocarbohydrazone is slightly soluble in cold, moderately soluble in hot alcohol; insoluble in ether and water. The alcoholic solution gives with alcoholic silver nitrate solution a yellow gelatinous precipitate.

Di-m-nitrobenzylidene-thiocarbohydrazone.

Thiocarbohydrazide (1 gm.) was dissolved in cold water containing a few drops of conc. hydrochloric acid and to the solution so obtained was added a hot alcoholic solution of *m*-nitrobenzaldehyde (1 gm.) with constant shaking. The reaction began with the evolution of heat and separation of a light yellow mass which was filtered off, washed with alcohol and then purified by boiling with alcohol. It was thus obtained as a light yellow powder of melting point 227°. (Found: N=22.62. $C_{15}H_{12}O_4N_6S$ requires N=22.58 per cent.). It is hardly soluble in ordinary organic solvents.

Di-cinnamylidene-thiocarbohydrazone.

Cinnamic aldehyde (0.8 gm.) was dissolved in alcohol and to this an aqueous solution of 1 gm. of the hydrazide hydrochloride was added gradually with frequent shaking. A yellow precipitate was formed at first but with the further addition of the aldehyde solution the whole was converted into an orange-coloured mass which solidified on standing for some time. This was filtered off and subjected to the action of steam to remove unchanged aldehyde. The residue after filtration was boiled twice with alcohol, which removed the greater portion of the tarry impurities and was finally crystallised from boiling nitrobenzene in yellow plates melting at 235° with decomposition. (Found: N=16.68. $C_{15}H_{12}N_4S$ requires N=16.76 per cent.) The yield of the pure compound was not good.

Di-cinnamylidene-thiocarbohydrazone is completely insoluble in water, ether, benzene and chloroform; very sparingly soluble in hot alcohol or acetone; readily soluble in boiling nitrobenzene from which it crystallised in yellow plates.

Di-o-hydroxybenzylidene-thiocarbohydrazone.

An alcoholic solution of salicylaldehyde (1 gm.) was added to the aqueous solution of thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride (1 gm.). To avoid the formation of a resinous mass, it was found best to add the aldehyde solution drop by drop. The reaction began with the separation of a yellow precipitate; after the addition of the aldehyde solution was over, the mixture was allowed to stand. The precipitate was filtered off and crystallised from acetone in almost snow-white shining plates melting at 190° with decomposition. (Found: S=10.31. $C_{15}H_{14}O_2N_2S$ requires S=10.19 per cent.)

It is soluble in alcohol and acetone, insoluble in warm ether, benzene and chloroform.

Di-anisylidene-thiocarbohydrazone.

Anisaldehyde (1.3 gms.) dissolved in dilute alcohol was added to 1 gm. of thiocarbohydrazide dissolved in water containing a few drops of conc. hydrochloric acid. The mixture of the two reactants was thoroughly shaken. A white precipitate was formed mixed with a small quantity of a resinous product and some unconverted aldehyde which rendered the whole mass pasty. On scratching with a glass rod for some time, this was converted into a brittle mass, which, after filtration, was boiled for some time with ether and then crystallised from acetone. It melts at 158° . (Found: N=16.22. $C_{17}H_{16}O_2N_2S$ requires N=16.37 per cent.)

The dianisylidene compound is insoluble in water, ether and chloroform; sparingly soluble in boiling benzene from which it is precipitated in an amorphous condition. It can, however, be readily crystallised from a mixture of acetone and water in light-yellow plates.

Di-furfuryl-thiocarbohydrazone.

From a mixture of 1 gm. of thiocarbohydrazide hydrochloride and 1 gm. of furfural a dirty brown mass separated out mixed with some unconverted aldehyde. On allowing the mixture to stand for some time it solidified. The powdered mass was freed from volatile impurities by means of steam and was finally crystallised from acetic acid. It melts with decomposition at 250°. (Found: S=12.02. $C_{11}H_{10}O_2N_4S$ requires S=12.21 per cent.) It is insoluble in water, ether and benzene; sparingly soluble in hot acetone but readily in hot alcohol from which it is obtained in globular aggregates. It can be crystallised from acetic acid in rectangular plates.

Di-piperonyl-thiocarbohydrazone.

To an aqueous solution of 1 gm. of the hydrazide hydrochloride was added about 1 gm. of piperonal. The mixture was then gently warmed on the water-bath and vigorously shaken when a yellow mass was obtained. Crystallised from acetone or acetic acid it melts at 195° with decomposition. (Found: N=15.10. $C_{17}H_{14}O_4N_4S$ requires N=15.14 per cent.) It is insoluble in water, alcohol, benzene and chloroform moderately soluble in acetone from which it separates out in rectangular plates with a faint yellow tinge. It is obtained from boiling nitrobenzene in amorphous form and from boiling acetic acid in light yellow plates.

Di-acetone-thiocarbohydrazone.

An excess of acetone was added to 1 gm. of thiocarbonylhydrazide. In the cold no reaction took place but when the mixture was boiled under reflux, the hydrazide began to dissolve in acetone and within several hours, most of the hydrazide went into solution. The solution was cooled and freed from a small quantity of an undissolved residue by filtration and the filtrate concentrated. When water was added to the concentrated acetone solution a white precipitate was obtained and this, for further purification, was again dissolved in the minimum quantity of acetone and precipitated by water as crystals which melt with decomposition at 195°. (Found: $S=17.06$. $C_7H_{14}N_4S$ requires $S=17.20$ per cent.)

Di-acetophenone-thiocarbohydrazone.

The mixture of the constituents in dilute alcoholic solution was shaken and finally heated on the water-bath for a few minutes. The filtered mass was treated with steam and the residue crystallised from alcohol in plates melting at 185°. (Found: $N=17.93$. $C_{17}H_{18}N_4S$ requires $N=18.06$ per cent.)

Di-benzophenone-thiocarbohydrazone.

No reaction took place on warming the reactants in alcoholic solution on the water-bath. But as soon as some sodium acetate was added, the reaction commenced at once with the separation of a white solid mass. After allowing the mixture to stand for a few minutes, the precipitate was filtered off, washed with dilute alcohol and then crystallised either from absolute alcohol or from acetic acid. The crystals so obtained melt slowly at 223° with evolution of white fumes and on being rapidly heated it melts at 230° with decomposition.

(Found: N = 12·68. $C_{27}H_{22}N_4S$ requires N = 12·9 per cent.) It is insoluble in water, benzene, ether, chloroform and nitrobenzene; very slightly soluble in cold alcohol and acetic acid, but moderately soluble in boiling alcohol and acetic acid.

Di-methylethylketone-thiocarbohydrazone.

Thiocarbohydrazide (1 gm.) was covered with excess of methylethylketone and the mixture was then heated under reflux till all the hydrazide was dissolved. The filtered solution was then concentrated when crystals of the hydrazone separated out. A further quantity was obtained by adding water to the mother-liquor. Crystallised from water the hydrazone softens at 215° and melts at 220° with decomposition. (Found: S = 14·86. $C_9H_{16}N_4S$ requires S = 14·95 per cent.) It is insoluble in ether, chloroform, benzene and alcohol.

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